

Figure 6E: P-S6 Film

P-S6

Figure 6E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-2 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)
Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Veh, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: MK-2206 (10 nM)

Lane 2, Lane 3, Lane 5, Lane 6 signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 6E: GAPDH for PS6 Film (TOP), GAPDH for Total S6 film (bottom)

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Lane 1: Sib-2 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)

Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Veh, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: MK-2206 (10 nM)

Lane 2, Lane 3, Lane 5, Lane 6 signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

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Lane 1: Sib-2 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)

Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Veh, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: MK-2206 (10 nM)

Lane 2, Lane 3, Lane 5, Lane 6 signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 6E: Total S6 film

Figure 6E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: Sib-2 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-2: **SC-79 (6ug/mL)**, Lane 3: Sib-2 **MK-2206 (10 nM)**

Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Veh, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 **SC-79 (6ug/mL)**, Lane 6: I-ASD-2: **MK-2206 (10 nM)**

Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows